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REAL-TIME DETECTION AND EXPLICIT FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION OF DELAMINATION IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER IMPACT LOADING

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SUMMARY: A new experimental technique is developed to determine the onset and evolution of delamination in fiber-reinforced composites under impact loading. The configuration uses a split-Hopkinson bar for low-velocity impact loading and two Polytec laser vibrometer systems for real-time monitoring of the initiation and progression of delamination. The experiment allows the histories of load, displacement, and velocity of impacted specimens to be recorded and analyzed. The recorded profiles are used to characterize the damage initiation and evolution in the laminate. Numerical simulations are conducted using a cohesive finite element method. The method employs a cohesive zone model to simulate inply cracking and interlaminar delamination and a transversely isotropic, elastic model to characterize the bulk behavior of each ply. The simulations provide time-resolved characterization of damage during the impact loading. The damage modes predicted by the numerical simulations agree well with experimental observations.

KEYWORDS: Composite Laminate, Low Velocity Impact, Real Time Detection, Laser Interferometer, Cohesive Finite Element Model

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymeric (FRP) composite laminates are susceptible to transverse impact. Low velocity impact on such laminates often cause damage that leads to significant reduction in the strength and stiffness of the material. Most of the damage is embedded inside the laminate and cannot easily be detected by the naked eye. Many structures using composite laminates are likely to encounter impacts by foreign objects in their service life. It is important to understand the mechanisms of damage initiation and evolution and to characterize the effects of such damage on the mechanical behavior of laminates. Experiments have shown that primary mechanisms of damage introduced by low-velocity impact include matrix cracking, fiber/matrix debonding, interlaminar delamination, and fiber breakage (Cantwell and Morton, 1991; Abrate, 1991, 1994, 1998; Joshi and Sun, 1986; Park and Zhou, 1999). The occurrence of these mechanisms has also been verified by numerical simulations (Zheng and Sun, 1995; Chang et al., 1990; Choi et al., 1991a-b, 1992). While mechanisms of impact damage are relatively well understood, there is still a lack of experimental tools that allow time-resolved analysis of damage initiation and progression. Most experiments so far provide only information on the final outcome of failure. There is also a lack of effective analytical or numerical techniques that allow the evolution of impact-induced damage to be explicitly delineated and predicted.

The First objective of the current investigation is to develop an experimental approach for time-resolved analysis of impact response and damage development. To this end, a

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split Hopkinson bar apparatus is used for loading and for the determination of histories of applied load, contact point velocity and displacement, mechanical work, and deformation during transverse impact of composite laminates. Further, a system of two laser interferometers is used to obtain differential surface velocity and displacement measurements at opposite sides on an impacted specimen. This combination of diagnostics offers a novel capability that allows real-time detection of the onset and progression of interlaminar delamination along with time-resolved analysis of full impact response. The coordination of the data on the time sequence of impact response and delamination development is expected to enhance understanding of the impact failure of composites.

Most numerical investigations reported involve various levels of simplifications. These simplifications are often based on assumptions of quasi-static loading conditions. These assumptions may lead to differences of 50% to 100% from experimental results. A dynamic finite element method was employed by Choi et al. (1991b, 1992) to account for the full field damage process. However, assumptions on the transverse tensile strength of various plies had to be made in their simulations. This approach did not provide explicit account of the damage process, which is essential in understanding the mechanisms of impact damage.

The cohesive finite element method (CFEM) provides a unique and powerful tool for analyzing damage and fracture in a material through explicit account of fracture. Since the discrete model possesses the attributes of both deformation inside elements and separation along embedded cohesive surfaces, fracture is an inherent attribute of the model and this approach does not require any crack initiation and propagation criteria. The cohesive zone formulation allows fracture to evolve as a natural outcome of the combined effects of bulk constituent response, interfacial behavior, and applied loading. The CFEM has been used to study a wide variety of issues regarding void nucleation (Needleman, 1987; Xu and Needleman, 1994), quasi-static crack growth (Tvergaard and Hutchinson, 1992), bimaterial interfacial cracking (Siegmund and Needleman, 1997), and dynamic fragmentation (Camboch and Ortiz, 1996). The results obtained, at least qualitatively, agree with experimental observations of fracture phenomena that are difficult to analyze using an analytical framework. A micromechanical framework for the simulation of crack initiation, nucleation and propagation in composite materials has been proposed by Zhai and Zhou (1998, 1999). Geubelle and Baylor (1999) used the cohesive finite element approach to study impact-induced delamination. They discussed the importance of including dynamic effects, nonlinear stiffening and finite deformation kinematics into numerical calculations to increase the accuracy of calculations. A computational model for predicting damage evolution in laminated composite plates was developed by Phillips, Yoon and Allen (1998). The second objective of this paper is to use the CFEM to develop a framework for analyzing impact response and impact-induced damage for composite laminates.

REAL-TIME MONITORING OF DELAMINATION

Abrate (1991, 1994) and Cantwell and Morton (1991) provided reviews of the experimental techniques and results reported in the analyses of impact on composites. The majority of the work focuses on the examination of damage after impact or the characterization of the post-impact behavior of the materials. Analyses of the influence of fiber properties, matrix properties, interphase properties and fiber stacking sequence are primarily based on the post-impact observations. Very few experiments allow for in situ or time-resolved monitoring of the damage progression. These postmortem analyses essentially use a snapshot at the end of the damage progress to assess material behavior and response. Clearly, real-time assessment of damage progression in a composite

laminate under impact loading is an issue of practical significance for understanding the behavior of composite materials. Due to the lack of real-time diagnostics, new techniques for detecting damage are needed to obtain information such as the initiation times and evolution history of delamination. The results are important and also useful in correlating the results from experiments and modeling.

High speed photography, acoustic emission and electrical resistance measurements have been employed to monitor the evolution of damage with varying degrees of success. High-speed photography was employed by some researchers to determine the onset and propagation speed of delamination. Takeda et al. (1982) used a small gas gun to impact laminated plates. Their experiments were limited to translucent composites. Recently, Hallett (2000) used a modified Split Hopkinson bar apparatus and high-speed photography to correlate the failure of impacted beams to abrupt changes in measured deflection. Acoustic emission techniques have been combined with microscopic observations to continuously monitor damage growth. Benmedakhene et al. (1999) used such a technique to study the effect of impact velocity on mode I strain energy release rate during low velocity impact. However, they were unable to precisely correlate the initiation of damage with acoustic emissions and had to revert to surface mounted strain gauges to determine the initiation of through thickness cracks. Abry et al. (1998) showed that increases in electrical resistance during monotonic loading of carbon-fiber-reinforced polymers are indicative of fiber breakage. However, the technique has not been used under impact conditions nor has it been shown to apply to other damage modes. In this paper, we present a new experimental technique for characterizing the onset and progression of delamination in composite laminates subjected to low-velocity impact. This configuration uses a split Hopkinson pressure bar for loading and two laser interferometers for detection of delamination through simultaneous velocity and displacement measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Figure 1 shows the experimental configuration for real-time detection of delamination. The material is a $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ laminate made from NCT-301-1G150(50K) epoxy

impregnated tape.

Fig. 1 Experimental Setup

The specimen is a rectangular strip 75 mm \times 18 mm in size and 3 mm in thickness. Its two ends are placed on two roller pins. The specimen is impacted at the center by a shaped indenter. A starter crack with a width of 0.3 mm is machined across the center of the longitudinal ply and extends to the transverse ply. Two Polytec laser vibrometers

are used to measure the surface velocities at one point on the front surface (impact side) and one point on the back surface of the impacted specimen. The lasers are aligned such that the two beams are co-linear and perpendicular to the specimen surface before impact. The lasers are aligned at a distance L from the center of the specimen. The velocity signals are digitally integrated to obtain the respective displacement histories. The difference between the surface displacements, $d=D_2-D_1$, is used to detect delamination, see Fig. 2. Positive displacement is defined to be in the direction of impact for both impacted and rear surfaces. The interferometers are capable of measuring surface velocities of up to 10 ms^{-1} with a resolution of 10 mm/s .

Fig. 2 Configuration for Real Time Detection of Delamination

Upon impact, the starter crack induces a matrix crack in the transverse ply that propagates in direction perpendicular to the ply interfaces. The matrix crack propagates towards the impacted surface until it reaches the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ ply interface where delamination initiates. The delamination propagates as a mode I crack away from the impact site. The response from an experiment with an impact velocity of approximately 4.5 ms^{-1} is shown in Fig. 3. The interferometer was placed 9.03 mm from the impact site. The impact energy, surface displacement, differential displacement and differential velocity history is shown. There is a significant non-zero signal in the relative displacement and relative velocity history at 2.2 ms indicating that delamination has reached the point of measurement.

The responses of three different specimens with an impact velocity of 4.5 ms^{-1} are shown in Fig 4. Surface velocity measurements are taken at different locations for these specimens. The time of delamination at the points of measurement increases from 2.2 to 3.8 ms as the distance away the impact site and the point of measurement is increased from 9.03 to 14.43 mm . This indicates an average delamination speed of 3.3 ms^{-1} .

An increase in impact velocity causes the time of delamination at the measurement site to decrease. In Fig. 5, the time of detection decreases from 2.2 ms to 0.4 ms when the impact velocity is increased from 3.5 ms^{-1} to 6.7 ms^{-1} . This indicates that the average delamination speed increases as the impact velocity is increased.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION

The delamination and matrix cracking are also analyzed numerically. The approach uses both an orthotropic constitutive formulation for the bulk response and a constitutive law for the fracture surfaces due to delamination and inply cracking. Fiber-reinforced composite laminates consist of multiple plies in a certain stacking sequence.

Each ply is unidirectional. The fiber cross-sectional area is so small that micromechanical modeling at the length scale of fiber diameter is expensive. To overcome this difficulty, each two-phase laminate is considered a homogeneous, transversely isotropic material. The fracture model is based on a cohesive surface formulation of Xu and Needleman (1994) and represents a phenomenological characterization for atomic forces on potential crack surfaces. This constitutive law for cohesive surfaces relates the traction and the displacement jumps across the crack surfaces. In the current study, a bilinear cohesive law implemented by Zhai (2000) is used to describe the constitutive traction-separation relationship. The model is used to characterize the effects of loading rate, loading mode and material lay-up on the initiation and progression of damage.

Fig. 3 Delamination detection

Fig. 4 Detection of Delamination at various detection points

Fig. 5 Influence of Impact velocity

(a) Shear crack model

(b) Center crack model

Fig. 6 Finite Element Model

PROBLEM ANALYZED

As illustrated in Fig. 6, two impact configurations are analyzed. In the first configuration, the beam is clamped at its ends and impacted at the center. This configuration is used to study delamination in a shear-dominated mode. The second configuration involves a small starter crack in the lower longitudinal ply at the center of the beam. This starter crack extends to the transverse ply. This configuration is used to study delamination under predominantly Mode-I (opening mode) conditions. The material considered is a cross-ply, graphite/epoxy laminate with a ply thickness of 0.8 mm and a $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ layup. The simplified layup in the analysis allows the essential features of impact response to be captured without numerical complications associated with a complex layup. The material properties reported by Chang and Lessard (1991) are used here. A constant impact velocity of 2 ms^{-1} is applied at the center of the upper surface of the beam. A 2D plain strain formulation is used.

Discretization of the specimen is based on triangular elements arranged in uniform “cross-triangular” quadrilaterals. Cohesive elements are placed between all element boundaries to model fracture in the forms of interply cracking and delamination. The cohesive parameters assigned to a cohesive surface pair depend on its location and orientation. A distinction is made between cohesive elements located within a laminate layer based on its orientation relative to the direction of the fibers in that particular laminate. Thus the cohesive surface parameters change according to ply angle and the

surface orientation within the ply. There is also a distinction between cohesive surfaces located on the interfaces between adjacent laminates and cohesive elements located within a particular laminate layer. In the particular mesh used, cohesive surfaces have one of the following discrete orientations: 0° , 90° , $+45^\circ$, or -45° . Elements located in the transverse ply have the same parameters regardless of orientation. The values for the critical cohesive stresses used are $E_{11}/200$ and $E_{22}/200$ depending on the surface orientation. Reported values of mode I and mode II energy release rates (G_{Ic} and G_{IIc}) are used to estimate the characteristic length Δ_{nc} . It is assumed that G_{Ic}/G_{IIc} is constant and $\Delta_{nc} = \Delta_{ic}$, therefore

$$\Delta_{nc} = \frac{2G_{Ic}}{T_n^{\max}} \quad (1)$$

(a) Shear Crack Model

(b) Center Crack Model

Fig. 7 Damage Evolution

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 7 shows the progress of failure in an impacted specimen with the distribution of σ_{\max} superimposed on the deformed configurations. The discussion here focuses on the evolution of deformation and failure. The results show that, for the case of the shear crack model, matrix cracks develop and coalesce initially within the 90° ply. The cracks subsequently propagate toward the interlaminar interfaces and cause delamination to occur along the interfaces. Delamination grows away from the impact site along the lower interface and propagates toward the impact site along the upper interface. The delamination propagates rapidly, leading to eventual global fracture of the beam. These results are in agreement with the experimental finding of Choi et al. (1991). In the center crack model, the starter crack causes a matrix crack to propagate in the 0° ply to the upper interlaminar interface. Delamination along the upper interface occurs subsequently from this point and grows away from the point of impact. The results show that delamination also occurs along the lower ply interface. This occurrence has not been verified experimentally.

The speed of delamination is calculated from the crack growth histories. The delamination speed for the shear crack model increases as the impact velocity is increased and reaches speeds above the shear wave speed (C_s) of the material (Fig. 8). In contrast, delamination in the center crack case propagates at speeds lower than those seen in the shear crack case, see Fig. 9.

Fig. 8 Shear crack delamination speed

Fig. 9 Center Crack delamination speed

CONCLUSION

Experimental and numerical studies on the deformation and failure of fiber-reinforced structural composites subjected to low-velocity impact are being conducted. An experimental technique for real-time monitoring of delamination progression in composite laminates has been developed. A framework for the simulation of the impact deformation and damage based on a cohesive finite element method is presented. This framework of analysis provides explicit account of material layup and fracture. The model allows fracture in the forms of interply cracking and delamination to be tracked individually. Calculated damaged modes and progression of failure agree qualitatively with experimental observations.

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